

Robust color chart detection using topological score diffusion

Pascal Baillehache

June 15, 2022

Detection of the QP203 color chart.

Abstract

This article introduces an algorithm to detect the location of a color chart in an image. Tests on a large dataset of various images show that it returns the correct location for around 99% of the images. It is robust to under/over exposed or strongly tinted images, and achieves better performance than one of the color chart manufacturer's dedicated software.

1 Introduction

Color charts are swatches of color used to detect color deviation in images. Since the reference values of the color swatches are known, they can be used to calculate the deviation of colors from the difference of their measured values and reference values. This deviation may occur due to varying illuminant, or bias introduced by the camera lens/sensor for examples. In a context where this deviation is detrimental, color correction must be performed.

The color correction takes as input the values of the color swatches in the image. These values can be obtained by manual color picking by the user, but for convenience an automatic way of detecting the color swatches in the image is desirable. The automatic detection must achieve two goals: locating the swatches in the image and pairing each swatch in the image with its corresponding swatch in the reference color chart.

Automating that detection task is challenging for several reasons:

- The color chart in the image can be rotated by any angle relatively to the camera frame of reference, hence the shape and orientation of the color chart in the image are unpredictable.
- The distance to the camera and the camera parameters are unknown, hence the size of the color chart in the image is unpredictable.
- The image may contain elements like a tiled wall or a checker board, easily confused with the color chart.
- If a color chart is used, it implicitly means that the colors in the image are somehow altered, hence relying on the colors in the image to match the swatches with their reference is unreliable.

In this article, a method capable of overcoming those difficulties and detecting correctly the color chart in various scenes and under various shooting conditions is introduced. It uses the Canny edge detector to identify possible swatches, filter them by heuristics, attribute scores based on the gradient of colors instead of the color itself to avoid being misled by the color distortion, uses a score diffusion method to obtain a robust pairing between swatches and their references, and finally calculate the location from this pairing using bilinear interpolation and least-square method.

The article is divided into sections as follow. Section 2 introduces related works and how they differ to the present algorithm. Section 3 introduces the algorithm, one subsection per step, with pseudocode and explanation. Finally, section 4 introduces the tests results and comments.

2 Related Works

In the thesis *Camera Array Calibration with Color Rendition Charts* by Behringer [1], the author introduces a method for color chart detection and color correction. The implementation of that method led to the motivation to improve it, and eventually to the algorithm described in the present article. Hence, there are some similarities (color patch filtering) in the first steps of

the algorithm. However the algorithm introduced here uses the Canny edge detection and flood filling methods, instead of a gradient analysis based on the Gaussian derivative. Further steps are also different.

In *Color Target Localization under Varying Illumination Conditions* by Bianco and Cusano [2], local descriptors are used to identify keypoints, which are then paired using the Hough transform, and the least-square method is finally used to estimate the pose of the color chart. The algorithm described in the present paper also uses the least-square method to estimate the pose of the color chart, but does not use local descriptors and relies instead on homogeneous color patches identification and their topology in the image.

In *Automatic detection of colour charts in images* by Palus and Kordecki [3], k-means clustering and filtering based on geometrical properties are used to identify the color chart's swatches in the image. The swatches are then grouped by clustering based on geometrical properties again, and the pairing is done by iteratively finding a linear transformation starting with a bounding box as estimate of the location of the color chart. This method differs from the algorithm introduced in the present article in both the way it identifies the color swatches and the way it pairs them with their reference in the color chart.

3 Description of the algorithm

The algorithm is divided into six steps:

1. Image preprocessing.
2. Color patches identification.
3. Topology detection
4. Score attribution
5. Patches and swatches pairing
6. Color chart location

Each step is detailed in the following subsections. The main function of the algorithm is given in listing 1:

Listing 1: The color chart detection algorithm.

```
img: image containing the color chart to detect, pixel sRGB values in [0,1]
swatches: number of columns and rows, and color values of the reference
swatches
FUNCTION LOCATE_CHART(img, swatches):
```


Figure 1: Example image

```
convImg = PREPROCESS(img)
validPatches = GET_VALID_PATCHES(convImg)
topology = GET_TOPOLOGY(validPatches)
score = CALCULATE_SCORE(convImg, topology, validPatches, swatches)
DIFFUSE_SCORE(topology, score)
pairs = PAIR_PATCHES(topology, score)
location = LOCATE(pairs, validPatches, swatches)
RETURN location
```

3.1 Image preprocessing

The image preprocessing consists of creating a converted version of the normalised image into the same color space as the reference color chart. The normalisation of the image intends to improve the homogeneous patches detection in over/under-exposed images.

The color space conversion step simply ensures that the values in the image (generally in sRGB) and the reference values (often in $L^*a^*b^*$) in the color chart are in the same color space.

Listing 2: Preprocessing.

```
FUNCTION PREPROCESS(img):
  FOR channel IN {0,1,2}
    min[channel] = MIN(pixel[channel] FOR pixel in img.pixels)
    max[channel] = MAX(pixel[channel] FOR pixel in img.pixels)
  low = min[channel] FOR channel IN {0,1,2}
  high = max[channel] FOR channel IN {0,1,2}
  normImg = COPY(img)
  FOR pixel IN normImg.pixels
    FOR channel IN {0,1,2}
```


of the homogeneous patches. These edges are used as the constraint in a flood fill algorithm on the image to obtain the set of pixels constituting each patches. The average color, center of mass and approximating quadrilateral of each patch is computed. The method used to obtain the approximating quadrilateral is the one described in Behringer’s thesis [1].

The patches obtained so far will generally contain many patches unrelated to the color chart swatches. A filtering step, similar to the one described in Behringer’s thesis [1], is then performed. The filter criteria are :

- patches with an area outside the range $[50, M]$ pixels are discarded, where M is equal to the image area divided by the number of swatches in the color chart.
- patches with non parallel opposite edges are discarded; the threshold used for the parallelism is equal to 0.15
- patches with an invalid aspect ratio are discarded; the threshold used for the aspect ratio is equal to 0.5
- patches with an invalid coverage ratio are discarded; the threshold used for the coverage ratio is equal to 0.4

Listing 3: Color patch identification.

```
FUNCTION GET_VALID_PATCHES(img):
    stdDev = 1.1
    sizeGaussianKernel = 4
    hysteresisThresholds[2] = {0.1, 0.25}
    edgeMap = CANNY_EDGE(img, sizeGaussianKernel, stdDev, hysteresisThresholds
    )
    patches = FLOOD_FILL(img, edgeMap)
    FOR patch IN patches
        patch.avgColor = CALCULATE_AVG_COLOR(patch)
        patch.centerOfMass = CALCULATE_CENTER_OF_MASS(patch)
        patch.approxQuad = CALCULATE_APPROX_QUADRILATERAL(patch)
    validPatches = FILTER_PATCHES(patches)
    RETURN validPatches
```

3.3 Topology detection

The next step consists of calculating the topology of the valid patches. The topology considered here is the neighbour relationship of patches. As the swatches are arranged in a grid fashion in the color chart, each patch is expected to have (except on the color chart borders) four neighbours located in the directions and at a distance corresponding to its edges.

The topology is thus obtained by looking for each patch for the neighbour patches nearest to the location

Figure 3: Patches detection

$$\vec{P}_i = \vec{C} + \vec{E}_i$$

where \vec{C} is the center of mass of the patch, and \vec{E}_i is the i -th edge of the patch. If a nearest neighbour is farther away from the expected position than the edge length it is discarded.

Listing 4: Topology detection.

```

FUNCTION GET_TOPOLOGY(patches):
  FOR patch IN patches
    FOR dir IN {0,1,2,3}
      topology[patch][dir] = NONE
      edge = patch.edges[dir]
      expectedPos = patch.centerOfMass + edge
      nearest = NONE
      distNearest = 0
      FOR otherPatch IN patches IF otherPatch IS NOT patch
        dist = EULER_DISTANCE(expectedPos, otherPatch.centerOfMass)
        IF ((nearest IS NONE) OR (distMin > dist)) AND (dist < LENGTH(edge))
          distMin = dist
          nearest = otherPatch
      topology[patch][dir] = nearest
  RETURN topology

```

3.4 Score attribution

Once the topology of valid patches is known, a score is attributed to each pair (patch in image P , swatch in reference color chart S). The score is calculated in two steps based on the color information and the topology as

Figure 4: Topology detection

follow:

$$\begin{aligned}
 score(P, S) &= s_c(P, S) + \sum_i^{nbCol-1} \sum_j^{nbRow-1} s_g(P, S, i, j) \\
 s_c(P, S) &= 1/(1 + \|color(P) - color(S)\|) \\
 s_g(P, S, i, j) &= 1/(1 + \|((color(P) - color(P_{i,j})) - ((color(S) - color(S_{i,j})))\|)
 \end{aligned}$$

$s_c(P, S)$ measures the similarity of the patch and the swatch based on their color. Given the color distortion, color alone is not reliable but it is accounted for to differentiate two swatches that would have the same relative gradient to their neighbours.

$s_g(P, S, i, j)$, where (i, j) are the column and row indices of the patch/swatch, measures the similarity of the gradient of color between the patch/swatch and their neighbours. The goal of s_g is to make the detection algorithm robust to color distortion. The idea is that approximately the same distortion affect all the patches, and that this distortion is mild. Hence, the distortion cancels out, or at least stay negligible when calculating the difference of gradients.

In the reference color chart the swatches are well defined by their row and column indices. But in the image, at this stage the pairing is not done yet, so the row and column indices of the patches are unknown. Moreover the orientation of the patches is unknown, and some patches may have been undetected, or inappropriately identified.

Missing/erroneous patches can't be avoided, thus they are ignored/treated as valid patches. Unknown orientation problem is avoided by calculating s_g for all 4 possibilities (rotations by 90) and keep the best one. Unknown in-

dices for the patch are set to the indices of the swatch in the considered pair (P, S) .

Finally $color(P_{i,j})$ is replaced by the color in the image at the location corresponding to coordinates (i, j) in the coordinate system defined by the vectors from the center of mass of P to the center of mass of two orthogonal neighbour patches according to the topology issued from the previous step. The origin of that coordinate system is set such as the row and column indices of S match P coordinates in the image. If that coordinate system can't be defined, then $s_g(P, S, i, j) = 0$.

Making the hypothesis that the color chart is entirely included in the image, pairs of patch/swatch leading to an expected swatch position outside of the image are clearly impossible. Their s_g is then set to an arbitrarily low value to ensure they'll be discarded in the following steps.

The combination of s_c and s_g gives a good indicator as results will show. However it is possible to improve the results by applying a score diffusion through the topology. It works as follow. For each pair (P, S) , its score is increased by

$$\sum_{dir} \max_{dir'} (score(P'_{dir}, S'_{dir'}))$$

where P'_{dir} is the neighbour patch of P in direction dir in the topology, and $S'_{dir'}$ is the neighbour swatch of S in direction dir' in the reference color chart. This operation is repeated a given number of times, 5 by default, and the scores are normalised at each step to enable a later thresholding.

In plain words, the score diffusion has the following effect. It seems natural that good pairs should tend to have also good pairs in their neighbourhood. By adding the best neighbour pair's score to a pair, all pairs will see their score increase, but correct pairs should increase faster. An incorrect pair wrongly attributed a good score (due to color distortion) should suffer from poor neighbours, while a correct pair wrongly attributed a poor score (due to incorrect topology) should benefit from good neighbours. By iteration, the score correction propagates through the whole topology.

Listing 5: Score attribution.

```

FUNCTION CALCULATE_SCORE(img, topology, patches, swatches):
  FOR patch IN patches
    FOR swatch IN swatches
      score[patch][swatch] = 1 / (1 + EULER_DISTANCE(patch.avgColor, swatch.
        color))
      bestScoreRot = 0
      FOR rot IN {0, 1, 2, 3}
        scoreRot = 0
        u = NONE
        v = NONE

```

```

IF topology[patch][rot] IS NOT NONE
  u = topology[patch][rot].centerOfMass - patch.centerOfMass
ELSE IF topology[patch][(rot+2) MODULO 4] IS NOT NONE
  u = patch.centerOfMass - topology[patch][(rot+2) MODULO 4].
  centerOfMass
IF topology[patch][(rot+1) MODULO 4] IS NOT NONE
  v = topology[patch][(rot+1) MODULO 4].centerOfMass - patch.
  centerOfMass
ELSE IF topology[patch][(rot+3) MODULO 4] IS NOT NONE
  v = patch.centerOfMass - topology[patch][(rot+3) MODULO 4].
  centerOfMass
IF (u IS NOT NONE) AND (v IS NOT NONE)
  FOR otherSwatch IN swatches IF otherSwatch IS NOT swatch
    gradientSwatch = otherSwatch.color - swatch.color
    expectedPos = patch.centerOfMass +
      (otherSwatch.col - swatch.col) * u +
      (otherSwatch.row - swatch.row) * v
    IF expectedPos IS INSIDE img
      avgColor = AVERAGE_COLOR_5x5_KERNEL(img, expectedPos)
      gradientPatch = avgColor - patch.avgColor
      scoreRot = 1 / (1 + EULER_DISTANCE(gradientPatch,
        gradientSwatch))
    ELSE
      scoreRot = -100
  IF bestScoreRot < scoreRot
    bestScoreRot = scoreRot
  score[patch][swatch] = score[patch][swatch] + bestScoreRot
maxScore = MAX(score[patch][swatch] FOR patch in patches FOR swatch in
  swatches)
FOR patch in patches
  FOR swatch in swatches
    score[patch][swatch] = score[patch][swatch] / maxScore
DIFFUSE_SCORE(topology, score, patches, swatches)
RETURN score

FUNCTION DIFFUSE_SCORE(topology, score, patches, swatches):
FOR step IN [0, nbDiffusionStep - 1]
  maxScore = 0
  FOR patch IN patches
    FOR swatch IN swatches
      updatedScore[patch][swatch] = score[patch][swatch]
      FOR dirImg in {0, 1, 2, 3}
        IF topology[patch][dirImg] IS NOT NONE
          neighbourPatch = topology[patch][dirImg]
          bestScore = 0
          FOR dirChart IN {0, 1, 2, 3}
            IF (swatch.col > 0) AND (swatch.row > 0) AND (swatch.col <
              swatches.nbCol - 1) AND (swatch.row < swatches.nbRow - 1)
              neighbourSwatch = swatch.neighbours[dirChart]
              neighbourScore = score[neighbourPatch][neighbourSwatch]
              IF bestScore < neighbourScore
                bestScore = neighbourScore
            updatedScore[patch][swatch] += bestScore
          IF maxScore < updatedScore[patch][swatch]
            maxScore = updatedScore[patch][swatch]
      FOR patch IN patches
        FOR swatch IN swatches
          score[patch][swatch] = updatedScore[patch][swatch] / maxScore

```

3.5 Patch pairing

At the end of the previous steps we have a reliable scoring of each pair (patch, swatch) to identify the correct pairs. However we still haven't actually done that pairing. Some incorrect pairs may still exist due to the correct patch being undetected in the first steps of the algorithm. With the view to filter out as much as possible these mismatches, the following pairing algorithm is used.

First, the pair with highest score amongst all pairs is added to the valid pairs. Then, iteratively until we can't find a new valid pair, the pair with highest score amongst the neighbours of the last added patch is added to the valid pairs. The idea here is to give priority to the topology, which is a more reliable information than the score (coming from the less reliable colors).

In some case, the topology is poorly connected and this pairing method would stop despite some pairs with a good score, and indeed correct pairs, aren't added yet to the valid pairs. To avoid that, when no new valid pair could be found, the pair with the highest score amongst not yet added pairs is chosen instead and the method described above continue. This would however force the addition of pairs with poor scoring, which is not desirable. A threshold, with default value 0.5, is then used to discard those pairs.

Listing 6: Pairing.

```
FUNCTION PAIR_PATCHES(topology, score):
  flagFirstPair = TRUE
  flagHasJump = FALSE
  keepPairing = TRUE
  pairs[patch] = NONE FOR patch IN patches
  flags[swatch] = FALSE FOR swatch IN swatches
  WHILE (flagFirstPair IS TRUE) OR (flagHasJump IS FALSE) OR (keepPairing IS
    TRUE)
    keepPairing = FALSE
    bestScore = 0
    FOR patch IN patches
      IF pairs[patch] IS NONE
        hasPairedNeighbour = FALSE
        FOR dir IN {0, 1, 2, 3}
          neighbourPatch = patch.neighbours[dir]
          IF pairs[neighbourPatch] IS NOT NONE
            hasPairedNeighbour = TRUE
        IF (flagFirstPair IS TRUE) OR (hasPairedNeighbour IS TRUE)
          FOR swatch IN swatches
            IF flags[swatch] IS FALSE
              IF bestScore < score[patch][swatch]
                bestScore = score[patch][swatch]
                bestPairPatch = patch
                bestPairSwatch = swatch
    IF bestScore > 0.5
      pairs[bestPairPatch] = bestPairSwatch
      flags[bestPairSwatch] = TRUE
      flagFirstPair = FALSE
      flagHasJump = FALSE
      keepPairing = TRUE
```


Figure 5: Color chart location

```
ELSE IF NOT flagHasJump
    flagFirstPair = TRUE
    flagHasJump = TRUE
ELSE
    flagFirstPair = FALSE
RETURN pairs
```

3.6 Color chart location

Once the pairing of patches and swatches is done the color chart location is relatively simple, given that what is meant by 'location' is properly defined.

From the perspective of the color correction goal, it is necessary and sufficient to know for each swatch (or as much as possible) the color values of the corresponding patch in the image. So far we already have calculated the average color of the patches, and we have paired them to swatches. This could be sufficient to perform color correction. Except that most of the time some swatches won't have corresponding patches, and incorrect pairing can't be totally excluded.

A location in term of coordinates of the center of the swatches is also known: this is the center of mass of their corresponding patches. A location in term of swatch bounding box is also known: this the approximating quadrilateral of their corresponding patches. But, in both case, it doesn't solve the problem of missing patches and incorrect pairing, even though missing ones could be located by extrapolating from known ones with the same method as when calculating s_g .

Another way to define the location is by considering the whole color chart instead of its individual swatches. It can be expressed with the coordinates of its four corners in the image. From these coordinates, a bilinear interpolation can be used to calculate the coordinates of the center of each swatch. The color at that coordinates gives the color of the swatch in the image. Note that usually an average over a small kernel centered on that coordinates is used to reduce noise influence. This method solves the problem of missing pairs, but requires to calculate the color chart's corners coordinates.

They can be calculated from the inverse of the bilinear interpolation on the known pairs as follow. Lets write the bilinear interpolation as

$$\vec{B}(col, row) = \sum_{i=0}^3 W_i(col, row) \vec{C}_i$$

where \vec{C}_i is the coordinates of the i -th corner, and $W_i(col, row)$ is the contribution (weight) of the i -th corner to the position of the swatch at (col, row) in the color chart:

$$\begin{aligned} W_0(col, row) &= (1 - y)(1 - x) \\ W_1(col, row) &= (1 - y)x \\ W_2(col, row) &= y(1 - x) \\ W_3(col, row) &= yx \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.5 + col / (nbCol - 1) \\ y &= 0.5 + row / (nbRow - 1) \end{aligned}$$

Each of the n known pairs gives us one equality where \vec{C}_i are the unknown, and leads to the linear systems of equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} W_0(i_0, j_0) & W_1(i_0, j_0) & W_2(i_0, j_0) & W_3(i_0, j_0) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ W_0(i_{n-1}, j_{n-1}) & W_1(i_{n-1}, j_{n-1}) & W_2(i_{n-1}, j_{n-1}) & W_3(i_{n-1}, j_{n-1}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{0x} & C_{0y} \\ C_{1x} & C_{1y} \\ C_{2x} & C_{2y} \\ C_{3x} & C_{3y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 & y_0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{n-1} & y_{n-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

which can be written as $WC = P$. Then, the coordinates of the color chart are obtained by calculating $C = W^{-1}P$. W is generally not an invertible matrix, but we can use instead its pseudo-inverse

$$W^+ = (W^T W)^{-1} W^T$$

equivalent to finding a least squares solution to the systems of linear equations above. This also means that if most of the pairs are correct, the impact of the few incorrect ones can be expected to be mitigated.

Listing 7: Localisation.

```
FUNCTION LOCATE(pairs, patches, swatches):
  iRow = 0
  FOR patch IN patches
    IF pairs[patch] IS NOT NONE
      swatch = pairs[patch]
      x = 0.5 + swatch.iCol / (swatches.nbCol - 1)
      y = 0.5 + swatch.iRow / (swatches.nbRow - 1)
      weights[0] = (1 - y) * (1 - x)
      weights[1] = (1 - y) * x
      weights[2] = y * (1 - x)
      weights[3] = y * x
      M[iCol][iRow] = weight[iCol] FOR iCol IN {0, 1, 2, 3}
      X[i][iRow] = patch.centerOfMass[i] FOR i IN {0, 1}
      iRow += 1
  MInv = GET_PSEUDO_INVERSE(M)
  location[i] = MInv * X[i] FOR i IN {0, 1}
  RETURN location
```

4 Results

To evaluate the performance of the algorithm introduced in the present article a metric and datasets were required.

For the metric, the Euclidean distance d_e from the location of each swatch to its actual location (obtained via manual annotation), and the Chebyshev distance d_c were used. d_c is compared to the size of a swatch, if for at least one swatch it is larger, then the location is considered to have failed. In other words, d_c gives a correctness metric. d_e gives instead an accuracy metric: how much the returned location is near to the manually annotated one.

Two datasets were used: one created by the author of this article using the QP203 color chart, and one provided by the Middlebury College's website [5] using the X-Rite ColorChecker Classic. Together, it makes 309 images containing one or the other color chart, in various scenes, under various shooting conditions, taken with various cameras.

The manufacturer of the X-Rite color chart also provides a free software able to locate that color chart. This software performance has been compared to the algorithm introduced in this article by manually running it on each images. No software able to locate the QP203 color chart was found.

Table 1 gives the failure ratio of the color charts using the X-Rite software and the algorithm introduced in this article. Results show that both are very efficient at locating the color chart in the Middlebury datasets, but the X-Rite software is less performant overall.

Strongly under/over-exposed and tinted images explain the poor results on the 'color-m' dataset. The algorithm introduced here appears more robust to difficult shooting environments. It is presumed this comes from scoring

Dataset	X-Rite software	article’s algorithm
Middlebury dataset (biwall)	6.6%	0.0%
Middlebury dataset (chalk)	6.2%	0.0%
Middlebury dataset (color-m)	17.5%	1.3%
Middlebury dataset (color-m2)	0.0%	0.0%
Middlebury dataset (color-m3)	0.0%	0.0%
Middlebury datasets (TOTAL)	5.9%	0.4%
QP203 dataset	N.A.	4.8%

Table 1: Color charts location, failure ratio

based on gradient of color and their diffusion through topology.

Results also show that the algorithm introduced here achieves equally good performances on the QP203 dataset. Color chart location failed on only two images: one where the color chart was so small that the color patches were filtered out during patch detection, and one containing a tiled wall which has confused the algorithm.

Diffusion \ Gradient	0	1	5	10	20
no	100.0%, Nan	95.1%, 3.1px	68.2%, 3.0px	53.6%, 2.9px	46.3%, 2.8px
yes	7.3%, 2.8px	4.8%, 2.9px	4.8%, 3.0px	7.3%, 3.1px	7.3%, 3.1px

Table 2: Gradient and diffusion effects (QP203 dataset)

Diffusion \ Gradient	0	1	5	10	20
no	99.6%, 2.7px	90.6%, 2.0px	77.6%, 2.2px	76.1%, 2.0px	73.5%, 2.1px
yes	5.9%, 1.9px	0.7%, 1.9px	0.4%, 2.0px	0.4%, 2.0px	0.4%, 2.1px

Table 3: Gradient and diffusion effects (Middlebury dataset)

Tables 2 and 3 confirms that the score based on gradient of colors and score diffusion are indeed key factors of the performance of the algorithm introduced in this article. The values in the table are (failure ratio, average accuracy) for some number of diffusion steps, and using or not the gradient of color in the scoring calculation.

Without gradient and diffusion, the location failed on almost all images of both datasets. Using the gradient alone or diffusion alone improves the location success. Using both together gives the best results. As the number

Figure 6: Normalised accuracy per image (QP203 dataset)

of steps of diffusion increases the failure ratio decreases or stay constant, until a certain number of steps where the failure ratio increases. The number of steps and use of gradient don't affect significantly the accuracy.

The same failure ratio for 1 step and 5 steps on the QP203 dataset can be interpreted as follow. This dataset contains rather easy images in comparison to the Middlebury's ones. If the score diffusion is unnecessary on 'normal' use cases, on more difficult ones it offers an improvement to the performance of the algorithm.

The increase in failure ratio after 5 steps of diffusion with gradient can be interpreted as follow. The diffusion has the effect of correcting the pairing score by progressively decreasing the score of less probable pairs and increasing the score of more probable pairs. During the first steps, the pairs with a very low score get correctly discredited. During the following steps, the correct pairs having a lower score than the other correct ones also get slowly discredited because their score increases more slowly. If the diffusion continues, those pairs eventually decay until they become considered as incorrect.

Figure 6 shows the normalised accuracy of location for images of the QP203 dataset. By normalised accuracy I mean the distance from the predicted center of the swatches to the manually annotated center, divided by the size of the swatches. As one would expect, best results tend to be obtained when using a good camera in good lighting conditions (from img16.png to img32.png). All distances are below 0.5, hence using the detected locations provide a reliable way to get all swatches color in the image.

5 Conclusion

In this article an algorithm able to locate a color chart in an image was introduced.

Tests using two datasets and two color charts have shown that it is independent of the color chart, and robust to strongly under/over-exposed and/or tinted images. A comparison with the software provided by the maker of one of the color charts has shown that this algorithm achieves better results.

The key points of this algorithm are:

- the detection of patches of homogeneous color using Canny edges and filtering heuristics;
- the detection of the topology of patches;
- a scoring function using the gradient of colors between patches;
- a diffusion method of the scores along the topology to reinforce them;
- a pairing of patches and swatches based on scores and topology;
- the color chart location by bilinear interpolation and least-square method.

The details of the algorithm in pseudocode were provided in this article, and the datasets used to test it are available on the Internet. Then, the implementation of the algorithm and the reproduction of the results should be straightforward.

This work could be extended with

- more tests on other datasets with other color charts;
- a more exhaustive study of the value of the algorithm's parameters;
- an extension to location of QR codes, Aruco markers, etc. which should be possible with minor modification of the algorithm.

References

- [1] Alexander Behringer. Camera array calibration with color rendition charts, 1987.
- [2] Simone Bianco and Claudio Cusano. Color target localization under varying illumination conditions. In Raimondo Schettini, Shoji Tominaga, and Alain Trémeau, editors, *Computational Color Imaging*, pages 245–255, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [3] Henryk Palus and Andrzej Kordecki. Automatic detection of colour charts in images. *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, 90, 09 2014.

- [4] John Canny. A computational approach to edge detection. *Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, IEEE Transactions on*, PAMI-8:679 – 698, 12 1986.
- [5] Ayan Chakrabarti, Daniel Scharstein, and Todd Zickler. An empirical camera model for internet color vision. volume BMVC 2009, 09 2009.

Supplemental Materials

The QP203 dataset is available here:

https://baillehachepascal.dev/2022/qp203_dataset.php

The Middlebury datasets are available here:

<https://skylight.middlebury.edu/~schar/colormatching/datasets/zip/>

Author Contact Information

Pascal Baillehache

baillehache.pascal@gmail.com